

A Prospective Interventional Study in PCOS Women to Evaluate the Role of Myo-Inositol Treatment in Respect of Clinical, Metabolic and Hormonal Effects

Dipanwita Bhattacharjee¹, Rakhee R Sahu², Vanita S Raut³

¹Senior Resident, Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology, Nowrosjee Wadia Maternity Hospital, Mumbai

²Consultant, Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology, Dr LH Hiranandani Hospital, Mumbai

³HOD, Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology, Dr LH Hiranandani Hospital, Mumbai

Received: 25-05-2024 / Revised: 15-06-2024 / Accepted: 01-07-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Dipanwita Bhattacharjee

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Polycystic Ovary Syndrome (PCOS) is a prevalent endocrine disorder among women of reproductive age, often leading to symptoms such as menstrual irregularity, weight gain, acne, hirsutism, and psychological disturbances. Myoinositol, a naturally occurring compound, has shown potential benefits in managing these symptoms due to its role in insulin signaling and hormonal regulation. This study aims to evaluate the effects of myoinositol on various clinical and metabolic parameters in women with PCOS.

Methods: This single-group study included 92 women diagnosed with PCOS, who received myoinositol supplementation for three months. Baseline and post-treatment assessments included menstrual cycle regularity, body mass index (BMI), acne and hirsutism scores, psychological symptoms, and glycemic status. Data were analyzed to determine the impact of myoinositol on these parameters.

Results: After three months of myoinositol treatment, there was a statistically significant improvement in several clinical outcomes. Menstrual irregularity reduced from 72.8% to 30.4% ($p < 0.0001$), and BMI decreased from 28.05 ± 3.88 kg/m² to 27.42 ± 3.76 kg/m² ($p < 0.0001$). Acne scores improved significantly, with 54% of affected women showing improvement. Hirsutism scores decreased from 9.48 ± 2.39 to 8.18 ± 2.39 , indicating significant improvement. Psychological symptoms decreased from 54.3% to 32.6% of the participants ($p < 0.01$). Glycemic control improved, with HbA1c levels decreasing from $5.97\% \pm 0.81$ to $5.56\% \pm 0.48$ ($p < 0.0001$). However, limitations included the lack of a control group, reliance on self-reported compliance, and the inability to perform differential analyses based on age or BMI.

Conclusion: The study demonstrates that myoinositol is effective in improving menstrual regularity, BMI, acne, hirsutism, psychological symptoms, and glycemic control in women with PCOS. Despite the absence of a control group, the significant improvements across multiple parameters suggest that myoinositol could be a valuable component of PCOS management. Further research with controlled trials is necessary to confirm these findings and explore long-term effects.

Keywords: Polycystic Ovary Syndrome, Myoinositol, Menstrual Irregularity, Acne, Hirsutism.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) is a multifaceted condition affecting women of reproductive age, often remaining undiagnosed. The Rotterdam criteria define PCOS by the presence of at least two of the following: oligo- or anovulation, clinical or biochemical signs of hyperandrogenism, and polycystic ovaries on ultrasound [1]. PCOS impacts 8-13% of women in this age group, with variations in presentation based on ethnicity [2]. Some populations show higher prevalence and complications, including psychological issues like anxiety, depression, and body image concerns.

Women with PCOS experience hormonal imbalances causing irregular menstrual cycles, hirsutism, severe acne, and primary infertility due to anovulation. They also face metabolic issues such as insulin resistance, weight gain, and obesity, potentially leading to prediabetes and type 2 diabetes. Pregnancy complications include recurrent miscarriages, preterm delivery, gestational diabetes, and hypertension, increasing the risk of future cardiovascular events. There is also a potential risk for endometrial cancer [3], although further research is needed.

In India, PCOS prevalence varies widely, from 3.7% to 22.5%, due to geographical and diagnostic criteria differences [4]. Rapid lifestyle changes in the Indian subcontinent, like urban migration and sedentary habits, contribute to increasing prevalence. Given the genetic and environmental complexities, preventing PCOS is challenging, emphasizing the importance of therapeutic options.

Therapeutic strategies for PCOS include lifestyle modifications, pharmacological therapy, and surgical interventions. Lifestyle interventions, such as diet, exercise, and weight control, are the first-line management, improving symptoms and quality of life. However, inconsistencies in study results necessitate cautious interpretation [5,6], and some women may require additional therapeutic interventions.

Pharmacological options include combined oral contraceptive pills (COCs), metformin, anti-obesity drugs, and anti-androgens. While COCs and metformin are established treatments, the latter is particularly useful for women with metabolic issues. However, COCs have associated risks, and metformin can cause gastrointestinal side effects and potential vitamin B12 deficiency [7]. Inositol, specifically myo-inositol (MI), is a promising supplement for PCOS. It acts as a second messenger, playing a role in insulin signal transduction, affecting glucose metabolism and insulin resistance. Some studies suggest MI improves serum SHBG levels and may benefit ovulation rates and menstrual cycles [8,9,10,11]. Despite limited evidence, the ESHRE consensus acknowledges potential metabolic, hormonal, and ovulatory benefits of inositol, making it a viable, safe, and cost-effective option for managing PCOS symptoms. This study aims to assess the efficacy of myo-inositol therapy in women with PCOS.

Materials and Methods

Study Setting and Design: This prospective interventional study was conducted in the Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology at Dr. L.H. Hiranandani Hospital, Mumbai, from December 2020 to May 2021, after obtaining institutional ethical clearance. Dr. L.H. Hiranandani Hospital is a multi-specialty, tertiary care teaching hospital serving women from Mumbai and nearby areas. Information about the study, including its purpose, was provided to participants or their guardians in their vernacular language, and confidentiality was maintained using anonymized data collection forms. Participants were included in the study after providing informed consent.

Study Participants and Sample Size: Women aged 18 to 40 years attending the gynecological outpatient clinic at Dr. L.H. Hiranandani Hospital and diagnosed with PCOS were included in the study. Exclusion criteria were women with Type 1

or pre-existing Type 2 diabetes mellitus, known thyroid disorders, and those with chronic hepatic or renal disorders. PCOS was diagnosed according to the Rotterdam Criteria 2003, which requires any two of the following three factors: oligo- or anovulation, clinical and/or biochemical signs of hyperandrogenism, and polycystic ovaries on ultrasonography. Women diagnosed with PCOS were referred to the hospital's metabolic clinic for multidisciplinary management and advised to adhere to lifestyle and dietary management.

The sample size was calculated using the formula $n = Z^2 \frac{1-\alpha}{2} \times p \times (1-p) / d^2$, where p is the expected proportion, d is the absolute precision, and $1-\alpha/2$ is the desired confidence level. Based on the study by Papaleo et al., [12], which reported a 40% success rate of singleton pregnancies, the sample size was calculated with an alpha of 0.05 (two-sided) and a precision level of 10%. Using nMaster software Version 2.0, a sample size of 92 subjects was estimated.

Data Collection: Baseline parameters, including age, ethnicity, education, income status, occupational status, marital status, and duration of marriage, were recorded, along with detailed medical, menstrual, and obstetric histories. Details related to PCOS included the duration since the onset of symptoms and prior interventions received. Clinical examination parameters included waist-hip ratio, BMI, acne score, and hirsutism score. Investigation parameters (blood) included fasting blood sugar (FBS)/postprandial blood sugar (PLBS), HbA1c, serum testosterone, lipid profile, and anti-Müllerian hormone (AMH). Ultrasound parameters included ovarian volume. Participants were advised to take myo-inositol therapy, consisting of myo-inositol 550 mg, D-chiro inositol 13.8 mg (40:1 ratio), vitamin D3 200 IU, and folic acid 5 mg, twice daily for three months.

Study Outcomes: At the end of three months of myo-inositol therapy, all clinical, metabolic, and biochemical parameters were reassessed and recorded.

Statistical Analysis: Data was entered into Microsoft Excel 2007 (Microsoft Corporation, Washington, USA) and analyzed using advanced Excel programs and www.graphpad.com analytics. Categorical data were presented as frequencies and percentages, while continuous data were presented as mean (SD) and median (quartiles). Data normality was checked before statistical analysis. Normally distributed continuous variables were compared using the unpaired t-test, whereas the Mann-Whitney U test was used for non-normally distributed variables. Categorical variables were analyzed using either the chi-square test or Fisher's exact test. A P value of less than 0.05 was

considered statistically significant, and $P < 0.01$ was considered highly significant.

Results

The study population consisted of 92 women with polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) at Dr. LH Hiranandani Hospital, Mumbai. The age distribution revealed that the majority of participants were between 26 and 35 years old, accounting for 65.2% of the total (30 women aged 26-30 years [32.6%] and 30 women aged 31-35 years [32.6%]). A smaller percentage of women were in the age groups of ≤ 20 years (7.6%), 21-25 years (13.0%), 36-40 years (10.9%), and ≥ 41 years (3.3%). Regarding educational attainment, more than half of the participants were graduates (55.4%), while 31.5% had completed a master's

degree. A small percentage of women were still students (5.4%), and 7.6% were healthcare workers. Among the 92 women recruited for the study, 4 were of European ethnicity, while the majority (88 women) were of Indian ethnicity.

The socio-economic status distribution indicated that 29.3% of the participants belonged to a lower-middle class based on the Modified Kuppaswamy classification scale, while the remaining 70% were classified as upper middle class. In terms of marriage duration, 41.0% of the women had been married for 1-3 years, 44.3% for 4-6 years, and 14.7% for more than 7 years. A majority of the women were married (66%), with one participant separated, and the remaining 32.7% were single (Table 1).

Table 1: Sociodemographic profile of the study participants

Variables	Frequency (%)
Age Distribution	
≤ 20 years	7 (7.6%)
21-25 years	12 (13.0%)
26-30 years	30 (32.6%)
31-35 years	30 (32.6%)
36-40 years	10 (10.9%)
≥ 41 years	3 (3.3%)
Education Achieved	
Student	5 (5.4%)
Graduate	51 (55.4%)
Masters	29 (31.5%)
Healthcare Worker	7 (7.6%)
Marriage Duration	
1-3 years	25 (41.0%)
4-6 years	27 (44.3%)
>7 years	9 (14.7%)

Among the total study population of 92; 67 women i.e. (72.82%) had complaints of menstrual irregularity; the duration of the problem is presented below. There were no complaints of menstrual irregularity in 25 women (27.17%). Among the 67 women experiencing menstrual irregularity, the majority had been dealing with the issue for 3 years (28.3%) or more than 4 years (25.3%). In terms of menstrual flow, 58.7% of the participants reported moderate flow, while 34.8% experienced scanty flow, and 6.5% had heavy flow.

Weight gain was a problem in 65 women (70.65%). There were no complaints of weight gain in 27 women (27.34%). Among the 65 women (70.65%) who had weight gain issues. Weight gain was a common complaint, with 65 women reporting duration details: 30.8% had noticed weight gain for 1 year, 32.3% for 2 years, and 16.9% for more than 4 years. The Acne scores were calculated based on the Global Acne Grading system. Acne was present in 43 women (46.7%), and absent in the remaining 49 women (53.3%). Acne was another prevalent

issue, affecting 43 women, with 44.2% experiencing it for 1 year, 34.9% for 2 years, and smaller percentages for longer durations. Hirsutism was objectively scored using the Ferriman-Gallaway system (FG score). Hirsutism was present in 31 women (33.69%). Hirsutism was absent in 61 (66.3%) women.

Hirsutism affected 31 women, with 35.5% experiencing it for 2 years, 29.0% for 1 year, and 25.8% for 3 years. In this study population, there were 61 married couples. Of this, 9 were not desirous of pregnancy at present. When it came to attempts at conception, 52 women reported their duration: 38.5% had been trying for 1 year, 32.7% for 2 years, and 9.6% for more than 4 years. Psychological symptoms were present in 50 women (54%). Psychological symptoms were absent in 42 women (46%). Psychological symptoms were also prevalent, with 50 women reporting various issues: 58.0% experienced low mood, 52.0% reported anxiety, 42.0% had a loss of interest, and 22.0% experienced sleep disturbances (Table 2).

Table 2: Distribution of symptoms and its duration of PCOS among study participants

Variables	Frequency (%)
Menstrual Irregularity (n=67)	
<1 year	4 (5.9%)
1 year	13 (19.4%)
2 years	14 (20.8%)
3 years	19 (28.3%)
>4 years	17 (25.3%)
Menstrual Flow	
Scanty	32 (34.8%)
Moderate	54 (58.7%)
Heavy	6 (6.5%)
Duration of Weight Gain Complaint (n=65)	
1 year	20 (30.8%)
2 years	21 (32.3%)
3 years	13 (20.0%)
>4 years	11 (16.9%)
Duration of Acne Problem (n=43)	
1 year	19 (44.2%)
2 years	15 (34.9%)
3 years	7 (16.3%)
4 years	1 (2.3%)
5 years	1 (2.3%)
Duration of Hirsutism (n=31)	
1 year	9 (29.0%)
2 years	11 (35.5%)
3 years	8 (25.8%)
>4 years	3 (9.7%)
Duration of Attempt at Conception (n=52)	
1 year	20 (38.5%)
2 years	17 (32.7%)
3 years	10 (19.2%)
>4 years	5 (9.6%)
Psychological Symptoms (n=50)	
Low mood	29 (58.0%)
Anxiety	26 (52.0%)
Loss of interest	21 (42.0%)
Sleep disturbance	11 (22.0%)

In the study, several key variables were assessed before and after treatment to determine the intervention's efficacy. Prior to treatment, 67 women (72.8%) had irregular menstrual cycles, which decreased to 28 women (30.4%) post-treatment ($p < 0.0001$), while the proportion of women with regular menstrual cycles rose significantly from 25 (27.2%) to 64 (69.6%). The mean waist-hip ratio improved from 0.824 ± 0.07 to 0.816 ± 0.06 ($p < 0.0001$), and BMI decreased from 28.05 ± 3.88 to 27.42 ± 3.76 ($p < 0.0001$). The average acne score, measured in 42 women, dropped from 9.023 ± 1.78 to 7.04 ± 1.66 ($p < 0.001$), and the hirsutism score, assessed in 33 women, decreased from 9.48 ± 2.39 to 8.18 ± 2.39 ($p = 0.012$). Psychological symptoms, present in 50 women (54.3%) before treatment, reduced to 30 women (32.6%) after treatment ($p < 0.01$), while the number of women without psychological symptoms increased from 42 (45.7%) to 62

(67.4%). HbA1c levels significantly improved from 5.97 ± 0.816 to 5.56 ± 0.48 ($p < 0.0001$), and free testosterone levels in 52 women decreased from 8.13 ± 5.2 to 6.63 ± 3.52 ($p = 0.001$). Anti-Müllerian Hormone (AMH) levels, measured in 71 women, also decreased from 6.237 ± 4.35 to 5.648 ± 3.08 ($p = 0.007$). Although the proportion of women with a normal lipid profile increased from 34 (68%) to 38 (76%), this change was not statistically significant ($p = 0.156$). The ovarian volume, assessed in 40 women, showed minimal change, with 20 women (50%) having abnormal volumes before treatment compared to 19 women (47.5%) post-treatment ($p = 0.765$). Overall, the intervention demonstrated significant improvements in menstrual regularity, BMI, acne and hirsutism scores, psychological symptoms, HbA1c levels, and hormone levels, indicating its effectiveness in managing PCOS symptoms. 23% of the women who were infertile conceived using only

myo-inositol as an intervention, without any other assisted reproductive technology (ART) techniques. Additionally, 13.4% of the women conceived with

a combination of myo-inositol and another ART technique. However, 33 women (63.46%) did not conceive (Table 3).

Table 3: Improvement in Outcome variables after myo-inositol administration among study participants

Variables	Pre-treatment	Post-treatment	p-value
Menstrual Cycle			
Irregular	67 (72.8%)	28 (30.4%)	<0.0001
Regular	25 (27.2%)	64 (69.6%)	
Waist-Hip Ratio	0.824 ± 0.07	0.816 ± 0.06	<0.0001
BMI (kg/m ²)	28.05 ± 3.88	27.42 ± 3.76	<0.0001
Acne Score (n=42)	9.023 ± 1.78	7.04 ± 1.66	<0.001
Hirsutism Score (n=33)	9.48 ± 2.39	8.18 ± 2.39	0.012
Psychological Symptoms			
Present	50 (54.3%)	30 (32.6%)	<0.01
Negative	42 (45.7%)	62 (67.4%)	
HbA1c (%)	5.97 ± 0.816	5.56 ± 0.48	<0.0001
Free Testosterone (pg/dl) (n=52)	8.13 ± 5.2	6.63 ± 3.52	0.001
AMH (ng/dl) (n=71)	6.237 ± 4.35	5.648 ± 3.08	0.007
Lipid Profile (n=50)			
Normal	34 (68%)	38 (76%)	0.156
Abnormal	16 (32%)	12 (24%)	
USG Ovarian Volume (cc) (n=40)	20 (50%)	19 (47.5%)	0.765

Discussion

This is a prospective interventional study, conducted from November 2020 to July 2021 in Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Dr. LH Hiranandani Hospital, Mumbai. A total of 92 women having Poly-cystic ovarian syndrome (PCOS) were recruited as study population. All of them were treated with an oral preparation of Myo-inositol + D-chiro-inositol (40:1) for a period of 3 months; re-evaluated them after treatment on different clinical, metabolic and hormonal parameters; to establish the role of Myo-inositol in PCOS women.

In our study of 92 women, 72.82% initially had irregular menstrual cycles. After three months of treatment with myo-inositol, this decreased to 30.43%, with 58.2% of women showing improvement. In comparison, Papeleo et al., reported an 88% improvement in 25 women after six months of treatment [12]. Ranwa et al., observed a 74.65% improvement in menstrual irregularities among 75 women, while Thalamati et al., noted a 42% improvement in their study [13,14]. Thakur et al., found that after 24 weeks of therapy, menstrual irregularity was reduced to 28.5% among 72 women [15]. Overall, the studies demonstrate a significant reduction in menstrual irregularity following myo-inositol treatment.

In our study, 92 women had an initial BMI of 28.05 ± 3.88 kg/m², which significantly decreased to 27.42 ± 3.76 kg/m² after three months of myo-inositol therapy (p < 0.001). Similarly, Thakur et al., reported a significant BMI reduction from 28.83 ± 2.3 kg/m² to 27.07 ± 2.70 kg/m² in 72

women after 24 weeks of treatment (p < 0.05) [15]. Bahadur et al. studied 36 women, noting a BMI decrease from 25.29 ± 4.1 kg/m² to 23.34 ± 3.14 kg/m² after three months of myo-inositol plus D-chiro-inositol, though this was not statistically significant [16]. In Singh et al., study, the BMI of 66 women reduced from 31.7 ± 1.64 kg/m² to 31.15 ± 1.74 kg/m² after three months, a statistically significant change [17]. Gerli et al., found a significant reduction in BMI from 35.14 kg/m² to 34.4 kg/m² in 47 women after three months of treatment [18]. Overall, these studies demonstrate a significant reduction in BMI following myo-inositol treatment.

In our study, 42 out of 92 women had acne, with a baseline Global Acne Grading System score of 9.023 ± 1.78, which significantly reduced to 7.04 ± 1.66 after three months of myo-inositol treatment. Notably, 54% (23/42) of women with acne showed improvement. Bahadur et al., studied 36 women with a mean acne score of 5.11 ± 3.51, which decreased to 2.80 ± 1.39 after six months of treatment with myo-inositol and D-chiro-inositol, a statistically significant change (p = 0.004) [16]. Ranwa et al., found that 20% of 75 women with acne had reduced symptoms after three months of treatment, with only 14.6% having acne post-treatment, and 33% showed improvement [13]. In a Thakur et al., study, 4 of 21 women (19%) had acne, which reduced to 4.76% after three months of myo-inositol therapy, though this change was not statistically significant [15]. Overall, these studies demonstrate a significant reduction in acne severity and scores following myo-inositol treatment.

In our study, 31 women (33.69%) presented with hirsutism, with an average Ferriman-Gallaway score of 9.48 ± 2.39 , which decreased significantly to 8.18 ± 2.39 after treatment. Bahadur et al., conducted a study with 36 women who had an initial mean score of 8.67 ± 4.60 ; after three months of myo-inositol therapy, the score significantly dropped to 4.86 ± 2.70 ($p = 0.174$) [16]. Thalamati et al., studied 100 women with a baseline score of 18 ± 4 , and after treatment, the score significantly reduced to 16 ± 2 [14]. In contrast, Ranwa et al., found a non-significant reduction in 75 women, with scores changing from 7.55 ± 3.70 to 7.2 ± 3.05 ($p = 0.355$) [13]. Thakur et al., reported a reduction in the incidence of hirsutism from 47.6% to 9.52% among 76 women, although this change was not statistically significant [15].

In our study, psychological issues were initially present in 54.34% (50/92) of participants. After myo-inositol treatment, this decreased to 32.62% (30/92), with 40% (20/50) of those affected showing improvement. However, 5 women required further psychiatric intervention. Jamilian et al., conducted a study involving 60 women with PCOS, evaluating mental health parameters using the Beck Depression Inventory and General Health Questionnaire.

After three months of myo-inositol treatment, there were statistically significant improvements in the Beck Depression Inventory (-1.0 ± 1.7 vs. -0.3 ± 0.7), General Health Questionnaire (-1.7 ± 2.9 vs. -0.5 ± 1.2), and Depression Anxiety and Stress Scale (-3.9 ± 6.4 vs. -0.9 ± 1.9) [19]. Cantelmi et al., reviewed the literature and concluded that myo-inositol significantly improves the psychological status of women with PCOS [20]. In our study, the HbA1C levels decreased from $5.97\% \pm 0.81$ to $5.56\% \pm 0.48$, indicating a statistically significant improvement in glycemic status. Thakur et al., examined 24 women and found that fasting blood sugar levels decreased from 95.5 mg/dl to 88.4 mg/dl after six months of myo-inositol therapy, with a significant reduction in fasting insulin levels from 14.41 to 11.19 ($p < 0.01$) [15].

Shokrupur et al., analyzed 26 women receiving myo-inositol for three months and observed a significant decrease in fasting plasma glucose (FPG) by 5.12 mg/dL ($p = 0.001$) [21]. Bahadur et al., studied 36 women and reported a reduction in fasting blood sugar from 87.50 ± 8.25 mg/dl to 84.58 ± 5.63 mg/dl, though this change was not statistically significant ($p = 0.084$). Similarly, the postprandial blood sugar decreased slightly from 103.89 ± 15.76 mg/dl to 102.03 ± 17.22 mg/dl, without significant reduction ($p = 0.634$) [16].

Limitations: This study involved a single group where all women received the same intervention,

without a control group to compare the effectiveness of myo-inositol against other medications. Women were followed up after three months, and all reported perfect compliance with the medication, though no measures were in place to verify actual adherence. Some women with normal baseline pre-treatment investigation parameters were not retested after three months of myo-inositol treatment, making comparisons impossible. The study included a heterogeneous group of women across a range of ages and BMIs, but it was not designed to provide an adequate number of participants for a differential analysis based on age or BMI.

Conclusion

It is concluded that, administration of (Myo-inositol 550mg + D-chiro inositol 13.8mg(40:1 ratio) + Vitamin D3 200IU+ Folic acid 5mg) oral tablet twice a day for at least 3 months or 12 weeks; along with healthy dietary modifications and physical exercise among women with PCOS leads to statistically significant improvement in majority of the clinical parameters, metabolic and hormonal parameters.

References

1. Rotterdam ESHRE/ASRM-Sponsored PCOS consensus workshop group. Revised 2003 consensus on diagnostic criteria and long-term health risks related to polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS). Hum Reprod. 2004 Jan;19(1):41-47.
2. Teede HJ, Misso ML, Costello MF, Dokras A, Laven J, Moran L, Piltonen T, Norman RJ; International PCOS Network. Recommendations from the international evidence-based guideline for the assessment and management of polycystic ovary syndrome. Fertil Steril. 2018 Aug;110(3):364-379.
3. Barry JA, Azizia MM, Hardiman PJ. Risk of endometrial, ovarian and breast cancer in women with polycystic ovary syndrome: a systematic review and meta-analysis. Hum Reprod Update. 2014 Sep-Oct;20(5):748-758.
4. Ganie MA, Vasudevan V, Wani IA, Baba MS, Arif T, Rashid A. Epidemiology, pathogenesis, genetics & management of polycystic ovary syndrome in India. Indian J Med Res. 2019 Oct;150(4):333-344.
5. Allahbadia GN, Merchant R. Polycystic ovary syndrome in the Indian Subcontinent. Semin Reprod Med. 2008 Jan;26(1):22-34.
6. Abu Hashim H, Foda O, El Rakhawy M. Unilateral or bilateral laparoscopic ovarian drilling in polycystic ovary syndrome: a meta-analysis of randomized trials. Arch Gynecol Obstet. 2018 Apr;297(4):859-870.

7. Amer SA, Shamy TTE, James C, Yosef AH, Mohamed AA. The impact of laparoscopic ovarian drilling on AMH and ovarian reserve: a meta-analysis. *Reproduction*. 2017 Jul;154(1):R13-R21.
8. Unfer V, Facchinetti F, Orrù B, Giordani B, Nestler J. Myo-inositol effects in women with PCOS: a meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials. *Endocr Connect*. 2017 Nov;6(8):647-658.
9. Morley LC, Tang T, Yasmin E, Norman RJ, Balen AH. Insulin-sensitising drugs (metformin, rosiglitazone, pioglitazone, D-chiro-inositol) for women with polycystic ovary syndrome, oligo amenorrhoea and subfertility. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev*. 2017 Nov 29;11(11):CD003053.
10. Griffith RJ, Alsweiler J, Moore AE, Brown S, Middleton P, Shepherd E, Crowther CA. Interventions to prevent women from developing gestational diabetes mellitus: an overview of Cochrane Reviews. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev*. 2020 Jun 11;6(6):CD012394.
11. Barthelmess EK, Naz RK. Polycystic ovary syndrome: current status and future perspective. *Front Biosci (Elite Ed)*. 2014 Jan 1;6:104-119.
12. Papaleo E, Unfer V, Baillargeon JP, De Santis L, Fusi F, Brigante C, Marelli G, Cino I, Redaelli A, Ferrari A. Myo-inositol in women with polycystic ovary syndrome: a novel method for ovulation induction. *Gynecol Endocrinol*. 2007 Dec;23(12):700-703.
13. Ranwa M, Nagaria T, Jaiswal J, Arya A. Study of effect of myo-inositol on menstrual irregularities and skin problems in polycystic ovarian syndrome cases. *Int J Reprod Contracept Obstet Gynecol*. 2017;6:2310-2317.
14. Thalamati S. A comparative study of combination of Myo-inositol and D-chiro-inositol versus Metformin in the management of polycystic ovary syndrome in obese women with infertility. *Int J Reprod Contracept Obstet Gynecol*. 2019;8:825-829.
15. Thakur SS, Anjum S, Siddiqui SS. Randomised controlled trial: comparing effects of metformin versus myo-inositol versus metformin and myo-inositol on ovarian functions and metabolic factors in polycystic ovarian syndrome. *Int J Reprod Contracept Obstet Gynecol*. 2020;9:2542-2549.
16. Bahadur A, Arora H, Ravi AK, Naithani M, Bahurupi Y, Chaturvedi J, Ajmani M, Mundhra R. Comparison of Clinical, Metabolic and Hormonal Effects of Metformin Versus Combined Therapy of Metformin With Myo-inositol Plus D-Chiro-Inositol in Women With Polycystic Ovary Syndrome (PCOS): A Randomized Controlled Trial. *Cureus*. 2021 Jun 7;13(6):e15510.
17. Singh P, Biswal S, Verma SK. A prospective randomised controlled study on the effects of myo-inositol on ovarian functions and metabolic factors in women with polycystic ovarian syndrome. *Int J Reprod Contracept Obstet Gynecol*. 2020;9:4912-4917.
18. Gerli S, Papaleo E, Ferrari A, Di Renzo GC. Randomized, double blind placebo-controlled trial: effects of myo-inositol on ovarian function and metabolic factors in women with PCOS. *Eur Rev Med Pharmacol Sci*. 2007 Sep-Oct;11(5):347-354.
19. Jamilian H, Jamilian M, Foroozafard F, Afshar Ebrahimi F, Bahmani F, Asemi Z. Comparison of myo-inositol and metformin on mental health parameters and biomarkers of oxidative stress in women with polycystic ovary syndrome: a randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial. *J Psychosom Obstet Gynaecol*. 2018 Dec;39(4):307-314.
20. Cantelmi T, Lambiase E, Unfer VR, Gambioli R, Unfer V. Inositol treatment for psychological symptoms in Polycystic Ovary Syndrome women. *Eur Rev Med Pharmacol Sci*. 2021 Mar;25(5):2383-2389.
21. Shokrpour M, Foroozafard F, Afshar Ebrahimi F, Vahedpoor Z, Aghadavod E, Ghaderi A, Asemi Z. Comparison of myo-inositol and metformin on glycemic control, lipid profiles, and gene expression related to insulin and lipid metabolism in women with polycystic ovary syndrome: a randomized controlled clinical trial. *Gynecol Endocrinol*. 2019 May;35(5):406-411.